

NEW MANUFACTURING PROCESS OF STEEL FIBER FOR REINFORCED CONCRETE

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ABSTRACT

Concerning the characteristics required for steel fiber mixed into reinforced concrete, though the quality of the steel fiber for reinforcement should be considered, the manufacturing cost of the fiber is still more important because the ratio of mixed steel fiber's cost occupied in the total cost of the reinforced concrete is quite large. Results of the investigation of estimated manufacturing cost for existing steel fibers indicate that the difference of the fiber's cost depends mainly on that of raw material employed.

This paper deals with a new manufacturing process which produces low cost steel fiber directly from cheaper raw materials such as steel ingot or steel slub. In this new process, a plane milling cutter is employed to machine a steel block. A needle shaped chip resulting from cutting is the steel fiber required for the reinforced concrete. The shape of the cross-section of this fiber is intrinsically triangle but quite changeable with the change of machining conditions such as the rake angle of the cutter, cutting speed and the feed of a cutting tooth. And the cross-sectional area of the fiber can be controlled by changing the depth of cut and the feed of a cutting tooth. This fiber has an irregularly rugged surface and an adequate twist along the length of the fiber, which effects the improvement in the slip-off resistance at the fracture of fiber reinforced concrete. It was shown that mild steel was most suitable for providing the fiber with proper stiffness and that its tensile strength was determined over 70kg/mm^2 due to severe workhardening during the machining operation.

The comparison test on the bending strength of fiber reinforced concrete using this machined fiber and the commercially available sheared fiber showed that the former was superior to the latter by 10% in strength. And from the manufacturing cost comparison between machined fiber and sheared fiber, the machined fiber was found to be produced at lower price by about 20%. Furthermore, stainless steel fiber can be manufactured by the same process. In this case, the fibers not only with triangular section but also with flexible thin foil section could be also produced by selecting the adequate machining condition.

INTRODUCTION

By the various kinds of tests, it has been already pointed out that steel fiber reinforced concrete(SFRC) has many superior points, i.e., high strength, high cracking-resistance and high toughness.^{1~4} In order to expand the wider usage of SFRC, it seems to us that not only the research and development of practical techniques such as the increase of strength, the working and constructing procedure and the application of various constructions, but also the development of production technique of steel fiber which is the most essential material is very important. The steel fiber used commercially for SFRC is not always satisfactory to the users from the point of its high cost and the wider application of SFRC is restricted.

New fiber production process using machining operation was proposed by one of the authors, T.Nakagawa to supply the steel fiber with better quality and lower cost. This paper deals with this new production process and the characteristics of the fiber produced by machining with the comparison of those of the sheared fiber which is used mostly at present.

PRODUCTION PROCESSES OF THREE EXISTING STEEL FIBERS⁴

Three different processes have been previously developed for producing short length steel fiber used for SFRC, i.e., cutting from wire, shearing from thin sheet and extracting from molten metal. Production processes and present conditions are as follows.

Cutting from Wire

Steel wire produced by conventional rolling and drawing is simply cut to the required short length. Cutting may be performed by mechanical press but a rotating cutter is preferably adopted to increase the productivity as shown in Fig.1(a). The section of wire is originally circular but it is partially pressed or embossed by rolling mill to increase the adhesive force. The surface treatment can be done on the surface of fiber before cutting the wire. The strength of this fiber is the same of the wire's strength, which is usually very high. This type of fiber is said to be available in USA and UK.

Shearing from Sheet

The fiber is produced by shearing the thin steel sheet whose thickness is about 0.25 - 0.5mm . The length of the fiber corresponds to the width of slit coil. In this case, in order to increase the productivity the rotating cutter is also applied for shearing as shown in Fig.2(a), where the cutter has about 20 cutting edges and its speed is 200rpm. Diameter of the fiber depends on the thickness of the sheet and the feed of the sheet. The feed of the sheet per one cutting edge is not less than the thickness and then the section is square or rectangular. With the bigger shearing clearance and the bigger roundness of cutting edges due to the wear, the fiber has the big burrs on its side which are rather effective for adhesion. Some of the sheared fibers have also irregular embossed surface to improve the adhesive effect. This sheared fiber is most common in every countries and most of steel makers are selling this type of fiber.

Extracting from Molten Metal

This fiber is extracted from molten steel by water cooled rotating disc as illustrated in Fig.3(a). The rotating disc has split spiral screws on its surface and molten steel touched at the ridge of screw is instantly cooled and the solidificated fiber is flown off. Its section becomes crescent shape and dog bone shape along the fiber can be produced by

Fig. 1 Cut wire (a) Schematic manufacturing process (b) Appearance (c) Cross-sectional shape

Fig. 2 Sheared fiber (a) Schematic manufacturing process (b) Appearance (c) Cross-sectional shape

Fig. 3 Melt-extracted fiber (a) Schematic manufacturing process (b) Appearance (c) Cross-sectional shape

modifying the ridge shape. Air quenched steel fiber manufactured by this process should be tempered to get adequate ductility. This process is proposed by Battelle Memorial Institute in USA. Stainless steel fiber obtained by this process is available in Japan, but it is said that this process is still under development for mass production and the main technical problem to be solved in future is to find the suitable material of furnace enduring for a long time in 1500 - 1600°C.

PRODUCTION PROCEDURE OF STEEL FIBER BY MACHINING FROM STEEL SLAB

This new manufacturing process of short length steel fiber is illustrated schematically in Fig.4 and has been developed by Institute of Industrial Science, University of Tokyo. In this process, steel slab is machined by plain milling cutter and the needle-shaped chip, which would be the machining swarf or scrap in conventional milling operation, is the steel fiber required. Fiber's axis obtained is parallel to the axis of milling cutter. This is main difference from the ordinary machined fiber produced by the turning with single point cutting tool. The length of fiber is determined by the width of slab or the width of cutter. As a substitute for steel slab, steel ingot or thick steel plate is able to be used for the work material. In the choice of cutting direction, there can be down-cut milling or up-cut milling according to the feeding direction of work material with the same rotating direction of milling cutter. Generally, down-cut milling is used so that the life of cutter may be longer than that in case of up-cut. Also from the viewpoint of the stability of cutting, down-cut milling is supposed to be more preferable.

In actual manufacturing, several numbers of milling cutters fixing abreast along the arbour cut the substantially large slab at the same time so as to increase the productivity. In case of huge ingot or slab used for work material, the rotating cutter may be fed instead of the feed of work material.

Fig.5 and Fig.6 show in more details the actual cutting mechanism for making steel fiber by this process. Very thin surface layer of steel is cut and piled up into triangular section. In the case shown in Fig.6, 30-40µm

Fig.4 Schematic manufacturing process of machined fiber

the depth of layer, average depth of cut, becomes about 10 times thicker in the final section of fiber. This is done by extremely large metal flow which leads to a large amount of workhardening. In addition to this, only 3ms is taken to produce a fiber in the ordinary cutting conditions such as $\phi 100\text{mm}$ cutter diameter and 120m/min cutting speed. Accordingly the temperature rise of chip reaches to a considerably large extent at the time of machining, because most of energy generated by plastic deformation converts to thermal energy.

Fig. 5 The schematic sections of surface layer of steel material to be machined and the machined fiber

Fig. 6 Enlarged machining operation of down-cut milling($D=\phi 100\text{mm}$, $S_z=t=0.5\text{mm}$)

CHARACTERISTICS OF MACHINED FIBER

Production Conditions Used for Experiments

Machined fiber was produced in the laboratory and the relations between various machining conditions and characteristics of the fiber were investigated experimentally. A horizontal type milling machine(No.3, 5.5kw, arbor dia, 1.5"), and a plain milling cutter with cemented carbide blades as shown in Fig.7(a), (b) were employed for the fiber production from a thick mild steel plate of 25 - 30 mm thickness. Cutting oil was not used in ordinal cases. The experimental results were shown mainly in the such machining conditions as cutter with 100mm diameter and 15° twist angle and down-cut except the special results.

Cross-sectional Area

Aspect ratio of the fiber is one of the important factors affecting the reinforcement. In this case, as the diameter of the fiber can not be defined because of the wide variety of sectional shape, the cross-sectional area of the fiber is used in place of the diameter. Cross-sectional area A and length L of the fiber are calculated from the following equations,

$$A = S_z \cdot t \cdot \cos\alpha$$

$$L = \frac{W}{\cos\alpha}$$

here, S_z : feed per one cutting tooth

t : depth of cut

α : twist angle of cutter

W : width of work material

Fig. 8 shows the actual cross-sectional area in various cutting conditions. A cross-sectional area of the fiber can be estimated from its weight and length. Each point shown in this figure is the average cross-sectional area of thirty fibers in the same cutting condition, because fibers obtained in the experiment have some scatterings in weight and section.

Fig. 7 Appearances of the milling machine(a) and cutter with WC blades(b) for the experimental production of machined fiber

Any sectional area A of the machined fiber can be easily obtained by changing S_z or t in the above equation. Usually, the fiber of 0.25mm^2 in its cross-sectional area so as to coincide with that of sheared fiber is produced. Among the fibers produced in the experiment, the smallest fiber in cross-sectional area is the one of 0.047mm^2 ($S_z=t=0.22\text{mm}$) and the largest one is that of 2.20mm^2 ($S_z=2.2\text{mm}$, $t=1\text{mm}$) as shown in Fig.9. To get the small and large fibers with less scattering, the milling machine having higher accuracy and rigidity is necessary to be employed.

Fig.8 Effect of the feed S_z and the depth of cut t on the cross-sectional area of the fiber

Fig. 9 Machined fibers with various cross-sectional area

Cross-sectional Shape

The machined fiber in general has triangular shape in cross-section as contrasted with the sheared fiber having square or rectangular. However, the shape of the machined fiber changes with the various machining conditions, i.e., difference of work materials, cutting directions, the diameter of cutter, rake angle, cutting speed, the ratio S_z/t of feed per one cutting tooth by depth of cut and so on.

The effect of rake angle on the cross-sectional shape of the fiber is shown in Fig.10, where the fiber takes thinner shape in cross-section with the increase of the rake angle. In actual production the cemented carbide blades with zero or negative rake angle may be adopted to prevent the chipping of the edges of cutting teeth.

The fiber produced in down-cut milling has a tendency to take a little thinner shape in cross-section in comparison with that in up-cut milling as shown in Fig.11. Also it is found that down-cut fiber has a whisker-like section which is formed at the final stage of the machining process. This increases the surface area of the steel fiber. Fig.11 also represents the influence of cutting speed on the cross-sectional shape of the fiber. The higher the cutting speed is, the thinner the cross-sectional shape becomes. As stated before, the cross-sectional area is determined approximately by $S_z \cdot t$, and then the ratio S_z/t can be varied in terms of the constant cross-sectional area. As to the effect of the ratio S_z/t , Fig.12 reveals that the fiber takes thinner shape with a decrease of S_z/t . As the ratio S_z/t decreases, ragged waves in cross-section as shown in the above figure take place. This wave increases the surface area of the fiber and is supposed to be effective for the increase of the slipping-off resistance of the fiber in the matrix concrete. From the productibility, the value of S_z/t is preferred to be smaller.

Fig. 10 Effect of rake angle of cutter on the cross-sectional shape of the fiber(up-cut, $S_z=t=0.5\text{mm}$, $V=22.6\text{m/min.}$, High speed steel cutter, coolant)

Fig. 11 Effect of the cutting speed on the cross-sectional shape ($S_z=t=0.5\text{mm}$, $\theta=0^\circ$)

Fig. 12 Effect of the ratio S_z/t on the cross-sectional shape ($\theta=0^\circ$, $V=116\text{m/min.}$)

Surface Geometry

Next to the cross-sectional shape, the characteristic on the surface of the fiber is related to the fiber having substantially great ragged waves on the free side surface of the fiber at the time of cutting, whose cross-section was shown in right of Fig.12. These waves are running to the longitudinal direction of the fiber as shown in Fig.13.

The ragged waves apt to appear in such cutting conditions as down-cut milling, higher cutting speed, thinner depth of cut, smaller S_z/t , and larger diameter and smaller rake angle of the cutter.

Fig. 13 Appearances of machined fiber with twisted waves

One of the two fibers has the waves nearly parallel to the fiber's longitudinal direction, but the other's direction of the waves does not coincide with the fiber axis. The latter twist waves are indicated more clearly in Fig.14 which illustrates schematically this twist wave with comparison of the sheared fiber. From the waves of longitudinal direction of the fiber with twist waves measured by surface profile meter, it is easily considered that this fiber has a high slipping-off resistance. This twist wave comes from the employment of rather large twist angle of the milling cutter. With the increase of the twist angle, the impacts originated from intermittent cutting were reduced at the same time the difficulty in manufacturing the cutter with bigger twist angle will be increased. And then the twist angle will be limited to 30 - 40° at most.

This type of machined fiber has naturally the bigger surface area which affects the adhesion force in the concrete matrix. From the Table 1 comparing the surface area in different types of steel fiber used for SFRC, it is understood that machined fiber has the largest surface area. Especially the surface area of the fiber having the ragged waves is wider by 50% than the sheared fiber.

These effects of cutting conditions on the shapes of the fibers can be explained by the change of shear angle shown previously in Fig.6. These tendencies agree with the results obtained by conventional milling and turning.

Surface Oxidation

By the use of cemented carbide cutter, dry cutting can be carried out, which leads to avoid the contamination by coolant.

At higher cutting speed over 70m/min., the surface of the fiber is covered with oxidized thin film due to temperature rise of the fiber originated at the time of cutting. Consequently the color of the machined fiber is generally blue, which is near to the tempered color of steel. The oxidized film acts as an anti-corrosive and protects the fiber from rusting.

Fig. 14 Comparison of surface geometry of the sheared and the machined fiber

Kind of fibers	(a) Cut wire	(b) Sheared fiber	(c) Melt-extracted fiber	(d) Machined fiber	
Cross-sectional shape					
Ratio of surface area	1.0	1.2	1.2	1.5	1.8

Table 1 Comparison of the surface area of four kinds of steel fiber

Tensile Strength of Machined Fiber

The tensile strength is one of the important factors requesting for the characteristics of the fiber. However, the appearance of bending fracture of SFRC shown in Fig.21 related later tells that the toughness of SFRC is improved mainly due to the slip-off resistance of the steel fiber. The excessive strength of steel fiber seems to be useless so long all fibers are slipped-off. The steel fiber is also requested to have adequate flexibility and toughness since the breakage and the bending of the fiber should be avoided during the mixing of fiber and concrete.

From the check of the tensile strength of the fiber produced from different kinds of steel, mild steel is the biggest in strength as well as a little toughness and flexibility. This means that the material must have sufficient ductility to endure the extremely large metal flow. Mild steel is also suitable from the reason why the material can be easily obtained with cheapest price and machining is easiest due to lowest cutting resistance and longest tool life.

Fig.15 shows the effect of cross-sectional area on the tensile strength of the machined fiber. Though finer fiber has a little smaller strength, most of the fibers have the strength of over 75kg/mm^2 . This value is just the twice of the strength of work material. The lower strength in down-cut milling is considered to result from the smaller workhardening and the lower strength in finer fiber comes from the lack of rigidity of the milling machine employed here.

Fig.16 indicates the relation between the cutting speed and the strength of the fiber, where the strength increases with the increase of the cutting speed. This may come from the air quenching of the fiber and the stable machining at higher speed of cutting. At practical cutting speed in over 100m/min , at least 80kg/mm^2 in strength can be acquired, which is of course sufficient for the steel fiber of SFRC.

Fig. 15 Effect of the cross-sectional area on the tensile strength ($S_z=t=0.5\text{mm}$, $\theta=0^\circ$)

Fig.16 Effect of the cutting speed on the strength of fiber($S_z=t=0.5\text{mm}$, $\theta=0^\circ$)

Possibility for the Production of Stainless Steel Fiber by Machining

A refractory or heat insulating material used at relatively high temperature for the furnace always receives a cyclic thermal stress which causes cracking of the furnace and shortens its life. The castable furnace material in which thermostable aggregates are mixed into cement is able to increase its strength against the thermal stress by mixing fibers into the cement just like the SFRC. In this case, stainless steel has to be used as material of the fiber due to its high heat resistance. It was already determined that a mixture of the stainless steel fiber into the castable fire-proof materials gave an excellent reinforcement. The stainless steel fiber has been produced by the shearing of thin sheet or the melt-extraction method. It was intended to confirm whether the stainless steel fiber of better quality at lower cost is able to be produced or not by the same machining method?

In comparison with the steel fiber, the stainless steel fiber generally has thinner shape in cross-section as shown in Fig.17. The stainless steel fiber takes thinner shape in cross-section with an increase of the cutting speed or the rake angle. Fig.18 shows appearances of the stainless steel fibers, where above one looks like twisted foil. By the present method, not

Fig. 17 Effects of the rake angle and the cutting speed on the cross-sectional shape of 18Cr-8Ni stainless steel fiber ($S_z = t = 0.4\text{mm}$)

Fig. 18 Appearances of 18Cr-8Ni stainless steel fiber ($S_z = t = 0.4\text{mm}$, $\theta = -15^\circ$)

only fiber being similar to the existing fibers whose cross-sectional shape is thick triangle, but also the twisted foil shaped fiber can be produced. This twisted foil fiber is supposed to provide with an excellent adhesion to concrete through its large surface area and its ragged surface shown in Fig.19. Further, this fiber is generally abundant in flexibility and has high productivity because such fiber can be obtained at higher cutting speed. Thus, this foil fiber seems to be quite promising one.

Fig.20 represents the relationship between the tensile strength and the cross-sectional area. Even the fiber of which cross-sectional area is the smallest, 0.04mm^2 , has a sufficient strength 70kg/mm^2 can be easily gained.

Fig. 19 Enlarged surface of foil type 18Cr-8Ni stainless steel fiber ($S_z=t=0.4\text{mm}$, $\theta=-15^\circ$, $V=116\text{m/min}$.)

Fig. 20 The strength of 18Cr-8Ni stainless steel fiber ($\theta=-15^\circ$)

COMPARISONS WITH DIFFERENT KINDS OF STEEL FIBER

General characteristics

Features of four kinds of steel fiber including machined fiber are summarized in Table 2. Here the machined fiber should be mainly compared with the sheared fiber which is mostly used. Judging from the investigations on the surface quality and the strength, the machined fiber is considered to be superior in the reinforcement or adhesion force to the sheared fiber.

Ability for Reinforcement

So as to estimate the reinforcement and the workability of SFRC using machined fiber, bending test by using the specimen of SFRC mixing the machined fiber into the concrete was conducted as shown in Fig.21, the results being compared with those of sheared fiber. Table 3 shows the cutting conditions and fiber's characteristics, the conditions of making test pieces of the SFRC and the condition of bending strength test. The machined fiber mixed whose appearance was previously shown in upper of Fig.13, has larger cross-sectional area than the sheared fiber used for comparison. Accordingly while the volume of fibers is equal, the former is less in number than the latter. The test conducted is the simplest one, 4 points bending fracture test; test pieces being square in cross-section, here fibers being mixed at random directions. These tests were carried out by Prof. K. KOBAYASHI's Laboratory, Institute of Industrial Science, University of Tokyo. As the workability at the time of mixing fibers into the concrete there were said not to have been any inferior points to the sheared fiber and moreover break-off of the fiber at mixing due to the lack of fiber's stiffness which had been anxious about, either, not to have been seen at all.

Kind of steel fiber	Characteristics of steel fiber						
	Appearance	Section	Surface	Surface area	Prevention of slipping-off	Metal structure	Strength (kg/mm ²)
(a)Cut wire	needle	circu- lar	cold drawn, lubri- cated	small	emboss- ing, bending	cold drawn	>200
(b)Sheared fiber	needle	square, rect- angular	rolled & sheared, rolling oil	medium	emboss- ing, bending twisting	cold rolled, annealed	45-80
(c)Melt- extracted fiber	needle, dog bone	crescent	temper color	medium	dog bone	quenched & tempered	40-60
(d)Machined fiber	needle, foil	tri- angular, crescent	temper color	big	twisting twisted waves	work- hardened	70-80

Table 2 Characteristics of four different kinds of steel fiber

Fig. 21 The bending fracture of steel fiber reinforced concrete

Dimensions of cutter	Cutting conditions
$D = 100 \text{ mm}$ $Z = 10$ $\alpha = 30^\circ \quad \theta = 0^\circ$ Cemented carbide cutter	$N = 200 \text{ rpm}$ $V = 62.8 \text{ m / min}$ $S_z = 0.75 \text{ mm}$ $t = 0.40 \text{ mm}$ Width for machining $= 30 \text{ mm}$ Down cut milling Without any oil
Tensile strength & cross-sectional area	
$\sigma_B = 84.8 \text{ kg / mm}^2$ $A = 0.28 \text{ mm}^2, L = 30 \text{ mm}$	
Flexure test of concrete by third-point loading method 	Sizes of test piece $; 10 \times 10 \times 40 \text{ mm}$
Maximum size of aggregate $= 10 \text{ mm}$ $W / C = 0.5$ $s / a = 0.6$ High-early-strength portland cement	Volume of fibers mixed into $V_f 1.0 \% ; 78.5 \text{ kg / m}^3$ $1.8 \% ; 141 \text{ kg / m}^3$ $2.5 \% ; 196 \text{ kg / m}^3$

Table 3 Conditions of investigations for reinforcement using machined fiber and sheared fiber

Fig. 22 Comparison of bending strength of SFRC reinforced by the machined and the sheared fiber (By the courtesy of K. Kobayashi)

Fig.22 shows the difference in strength between the two, and indicates that the machined fiber has greater bending strength by approximately 10% than the sheared fiber in spite of the former being less in number than the latter. This is supposed to originate from causes, i.e., high adhesion attributing to both its large surface area and its moderate ragged waves on the surface. As to the reinforcement, several results in addition to this were already obtained, each of which indicates that the machined fiber is superior to some extent to the sheared fiber. Especially the fiber having prominent ragged waves on its surface shown in lower of Fig.13 has biggest ability of reinforcement.

Production Cost

Fiber cost will be divided into 3 parts, i.e., material costs, manufacturing costs and other costs, for example, associated with packaging and transporting. Here, the production cost of the machined fiber is mainly related in comparison with that of the sheared fiber.

The difference in productive rate between the two can be easily elucidated since both of them utilize rotating cutters. In case of 20 teeth and 250rpm revolutions, 5000 per minute or 300,000 fibers per hour can be produced. If a fiber weighs 60mg, the fibers of 18kg are produced for an hour. The production rate per a day amount to 90kg in 5 hours operation,

or to 180kg in 10 hours. In case of 10 cutters mounting on the single axis, it may amount to 900 - 1800kg a day, and the machine may produce 1 - 2 ton a day of 200 - 400ton a year. As to the machined fiber, as the cutter of 200mm in diameter is applied, the cutting speed reaches approximately 150m/min. As twice of this speed is supposed to be the upper limit in the cutting speed, by the use of cemented carbide cutter it is possible to make this productive rate twice. Thus, there is supposed not to be much difference in the productive rate between the two.

It is well known that costs charged for packaging and transporting hold substantially large parts in the fiber's cost. However, such cost is charged commonly between all kinds of fibers. Therefore, cost for tools,labours or depreciation of installations may be comparable factors. Automated machine will be utilized in both of them, in consequence, labour cost is common between the two, and then the rests, i.e., cost for tools and depreciation for facilities are the matters mainly discussed about. While the production facilities of machined fiber under the conditions as stated above are not estimated to cost much more expensively than those of the sheared fiber. With regard to the tool cost, precise test to determine the tool life was not conducted. However, even if the sheared fiber costs half of the machined fiber in their tool costs, this cost difference coincides with the cost of slitting the coil material and the treatment of removing rolling oil which is necessary in case of the sheared fiber. After all there is almost no difference in manufacturing cost between them.

From the bases of the above discussions, cost comparisons of each fiber indicated in Table 4 was performed. The cost difference results in mainly that of material cost. The machined fiber produced from slab or ingot which is cheaper than the thin sheets is considered to be superior to the sheared fiber. In this sence, melt extracted fiber is the most economical fiber due to being made from the cheapest molten metal obtained from scrap. Though it is important to obtain cheaper materials, the cost of packaging and transporting will be very important factors because both of them occupy substantially large rate in whole cost.

Kinds of fibers \ Cost	Material	Production	Packing & transportation	Total
(a) Cut wire	160	30	50	240
(b) Sheared fiber	80	40*	50	170
(c) Melt-extracted fiber	30	40	50	120**
(d) Machined fiber	50	40	50	140

(Unit= x1000yen/ton, *Including a slitting cost,**10000ton/year)

Table 4 Cost analysis of various steel fiber in the production scale of 1000 ton/year

CONCLUSIONS

New manufacturing process of steel fiber by machining for SFRC was proposed and the steel fiber produced experimentally was confirmed to have sufficient quality for use by selecting a suitable machining condition. From the comparison with other existing steel fibers, this machining fiber is quite hopeful both in the quality and in the fiber cost. This machined fiber manufactured by specially developed pilot machine is now offered to the users from Aida Engineering Co. in Japan. It is said that its machined fiber has better ability for reinforcement than that related in this paper. This means that the machined fiber will be further more economical because the content percentage of fiber mixing into concrete can be reduced so as to get the equivalent strength of SFRC. The authors believe that the machined fiber has the possibility to be improved much more in future from the viewpoint of quality.

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